

Relativistic Rest Mass Energy Arising From Nonrelativistic Quantum Mechanics?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 19, 2024

It is sometimes noted in the literature (1) that a constant velocity classical particle has a probability $P(x)dx=dx/L$ ((1)). This statement seems to be based on the idea that the amount of time spent by the particle in each dx region is a constant dt . A deterministic particle, however, does not appear to be associated with any uncertainty and hence probability. In order to introduce the notion of probability, one must not follow the particle classically, i.e. in x,t . Furthermore, probability is supposed to be associated with maximum entropy (subject to constraints) and all possible bias should be removed. A particle which moves in one direction has bias in that direction and classical probability should remove all bias. Thus, we argue that the statement ((1)) only makes sense if one has velocity (or momentum) to both the right and left. This is not an OR statement, it is an AND statement in probability. Thus, $1/L = P(p,x)P(-p,x)$ with p and $-p$ being time reversed (movie playing backward) scenarios (2).

Furthermore, a lack of bias is associated with the maximization of entropy subject to constraints. In previous notes, we suggested that one obtain $\exp(ipx)$ by maximizing $P(p,x) \ln(P(p,x)) + ipx P(p,x)$. Here we try to use maximize Shannon's entropy using probability= $P(p,x)P(-p,x)$ subject to two constraints: $P(-p,x)P(p,x)=1/L$ and $\langle x \text{ for } p \rangle = - \langle x \text{ for } -p \rangle$. This, we argue, leads to $\exp(ipx)$.

At present, all arguments are performed for in the nonrelativistic situation although the above could just as well apply to relativistic p . Playing a moving backwards to obtain $-p$ from p is the same as considering $x \rightarrow -x$ and this suggests that one consider $t \rightarrow -t$. We argue that the conditions which require $P(-p,x)P(p,x)=1/L$ should hold for $P(E, t)P(E,-t) = 1/T$. If this is the case, then one has: $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, where $E=pp/2m_0$ and $p=mv$. One may, however, view the system from a moving frame in which $p=0$. If one uses $E=pp/2m$, then $E=0$ and probability is 0 in this frame, but nonzero in the other. This cannot be as probability is invariant and so one cannot use $E=pp/2m$, but must find an energy which is nonzero even when the particle is not moving. This, we argue, leads to the notion of rest mass with $-Et+px$ being an invariant in all frames.

Classical Particle with Constant Velocity and the Notion of Probability

One sometimes sees the probability expression $P(x)dx = C/v(v)$, where $.5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ (1). For a constant velocity, i.e. no $V(x)$:

$P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length ((1))

A deterministic particle moving as $x=vt$, however, has no uncertainty and it is not clear why there should be any probability. If one does not follow the particle as $x=vt$, however, there may be uncertainty as to its location. Probability, however, is usually obtained by maximizing entropy subject to constraints. It seems that one tries to remove as much bias as possible when finding probabilities which maximize entropy. A particle moving in one direction, however, has bias in that direction. Thus, we suggest that ((1)) is incompatible with a particle moving in one direction (in a one-dimensional scenario). This requires:

p AND $-p$ (not p or $-p$) which is equivalent to: $P(p,x)P(-p,x) = 1/L$ ((2))

This still does not give the form for $P(p,x)$. We next suggest that one maximize entropy subject to two constraints:

((2)) and $\langle x \text{ for } p \rangle = \langle x \text{ for } -p \rangle$ ((3))

One may maximize: $-P(p,x)P(-p,x) \ln\{P(p,x)P(-p,x)\} + b (xP(p,x) + xP(-p,x))$ ((4))

where b is a Lagrange multiplier and the constraint ((2)) will be imposed "by hand" ((4)) leads to:

$P(p,x) = \exp(ix)$ but ((2)) must apply so $b = F(\text{odd})(p)$ where F is an unknown odd function of p so that ((2)) applies.

To find $F(p)$, one may use the idea of $d/dx \ln\{P(p,x)\}$ which we suggest is similar to using a derivative in Fisher information. $\ln(P(p,x))$ is information and should tell one about x and p , not about $F(p)$. In other words, the information is p , not some odd function of p and so we suggest that:

$d/dx \ln(P(p,x)) = p$ ((5))

This ultimately leads to: $P(p,x) = 1/\sqrt{L} \exp(ipx)$ ((6))

((6)) is a biased or dynamical probability associated with a certain direction of motion (2).

The "i" is introduced so that the probability does not grow or shrink indefinitely.

Thus, strong consequences follow from considering $P(x)dx = 1dx/L$.

One might ask: Why is p not associated with both x and t ? Given that $x=vt$, even for a photon, if one had t in the probability, one could replace it with x/v . Given a momentum, there must be motion and so there must be a change in x . The change in t is a consequence of the change in x for a constant v .

Playing a Movie Backwards

We suggested in (3) that given p , $-p$ follows from "playing the movie backwards". If one has a dx about x and suggests that dt is constant, one may, using the notion of spacetime, argue that this is equivalent to having a dt about t with dx constant. Instead of using p and x , we suggest using E and t , i.e.

$P(E,t) = \exp(-iEt)$ ((7))

In the nonrelativistic scenario, $E=pp/2m$, but we suggested above that p is associated with x because motion implies x must change. $E=pp/2m$ is also linked with motion, but includes p and $-p$ and so on average one need not have position change. This, however, also points to the notion of an energy at rest at a position x_1 , such that only t changes. We argue later that this is in fact the case, but at present only consider the nonrelativistic $E =pp/2m$. Why should one use $-E$ in ((7)) and p or $-p$ in ((6)). We argue that for a photon (which may also be considered), one wishes to have $-E dt + p dx =0 \rightarrow dx/dt = E/p$, hence $-E$.

Thus, the full directional (or dynamic probability (1)) is: $\exp(-iEt+ipx) 1/\sqrt{L}$ ((8))

Relativistic Rest Mass Energy

If ((8)) represents probability, then a difficulty arises if one views the system from a frame moving with velocity v , corresponding to the v in $p=mv$. In particular, ((8)) is nonzero if the particle is viewed moving, but in the rest frame, $E=pp/2m=0$ and $p=0$ and probability is $1/\sqrt{L}$. Probability must be the same in all frames, this suggests that:

$-Et+px$ is frame independent ((9))

In the frame for which $p=0$, one has probability = $\exp(-Et)$ so E cannot be $pp/2m$. We suggest that rest mass (multiplied by a constant) must represent energy. This is also in keeping with E linked with t , which changes even if x does not. ((9)) is a condition for a Lorentz invariant. Thus, we argue that ideas of special relativity emerge from nonrelativistic quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may consider the probability of a particle with constant p , v nonrelativistically. Probability suggests as little bias as possible and so $P(x)dx=dx/L$ implies that one must have p AND $-p$. We use p because it is linked to impulse. Probability is based on the removal of bias and a particle moving in one direction has bias. Thus: $P(p,x)P(-p,x)dx = dx/L$. We suggest that given p , $-p$ is obtained by playing the movie backwards (2).

We proceed to maximize Shannon's entropy using $P(p,x)P(-p,x)$ =probability for two constraints: $\langle x \text{ for } p \rangle - \langle x \text{ for } -p \rangle =0$ and $P(p,x)P(-p,x) = 1/L$. The latter we put in by hand. This leads to: $\exp(i F(\text{odd})(p) x)$. We argue that if $\ln(P(p,x))$ is information then d/dx of this information should remove x and reveal the second piece of information in the problem which should be p . Thus $F(\text{odd})(p) =p$.

Given that one may play a movie backwards and that dx about x represents constant dt , one may write: dt about t represents constant x and postulate $\exp(+/- i Et)$. "i" is used so the dynamical probability does not grow or shrink indefinitely. A minus sign is chosen, i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$, so that for a photon $-E dt + p dx=0$. One may note that p is linked with x because motion implies a change in x . One could have a piece proportional to t , but $x=vt$ and t may be replaced with x . Why does this reasoning not apply to $-Et$? We suggest that even for no motion, there should be an E , (i.e. rest energy) so that t changes even if x does not. Not make this idea more formal, we consider $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If $E=pp/2m_0$ and $p=mv$, then in the frame which sees the particle move

there is nonzero probability, but in a rest frame probability is 0. This cannot be, so E should be rest energy, we suggest and $-Et+px$ should be a frame invariant. These ideas already point to special relativity as $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant. This suggests that (x,t) and (p,E) should transform the same way. It is possible to find a Lorentz transformation matrix for (x,t) and if one applies this to $(0, m_0c^2)$ as rest energy, then one finds: $p=mv/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $E=m_0c^2/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ which in the nonrelativistic limit yields the proper nonrelativistic results.

References

1. Majernick, V and Opalmy, T. Entropic Uncertainty Relations for the Quantum Oscillator (1999, Journal of Physics A Mathematical and General 29(9):2187
DOI:[10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029](https://doi.org/10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029)
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Dynamical Probability Wave (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Time Reversal and Wavefunction*(x,t)Wavefunction(x,t) (preprint, zenodo, 2022)